

Anvarbek Turdialiyev

Toshkent davlat o'zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti tayanch doktoranti

Annotation. When determining the focal point of the Surkhandarya dialect zone, the city of Termiz is defined as a weak focal point, which indicates that the dialect of the region is not well studied. In this article, the Denov district dialect of Surkhandarya region is analyzed. The influence of the studied regional dialect on neighboring dialects and, conversely, the influence of the neighboring dialect and the Tajik language on the regional dialect were studied by comparing the morphological features of existing places.

Keywords. dialect, dialect zone, territory, area, conjugation, tense, verb, affix.

When determining the focal point of the Surkhandarya dialect zone, the city of Termiz is defined as a weak focal point, which indicates that the dialect of the region is not well studied. In this article, the Denov district dialect of Surkhandarya region is analyzed.

According to the phonetic, grammatical, lexical features of the Karaganda dialects in the dialectal zone, they can be divided into

2. Morphological features of the I-type Karak dialects:

It is a 5-conjugate system, and nominative conjugation is also represented by the subjunctive conjugation. For example, the book of oneself (adab.) *ozinī kitābi*, the water of a river (adab.) *dajrāni suvi*.

The accusative agreement is represented by the affixes *-ni/-di/-ti* in the dialect. Affixes *-ni* (*bizani*), after voiced consonants *-di* (*ojdi*), and voiceless consonants *-ti* (*gošti*) are used after vowels. We can observe this situation in the dialects of Tashkent region¹.

The plural is used in the form *-lār* in the same way as in the literary language. This affix expresses the meaning of respect together with the plural. In particular, this situation is being actively used later as a result of the influence of the literary language and type II Karaganda dialects.

The affixes *-di/ti* are used to express the definite past tense. After vowels and voiced consonants, the suffix *-di* is used (*bārdi, keldi, turdi, ushledi*), and after voiceless consonants, the suffix *-ti* (*otti, ketti, išti (ichdi), bāšti*) is used.

When expressing the long past tense, the analytic forms of the verb *-gān edi, -jātgān edi, -(ā)r edi*, together with the single *-gan/-kān/-qān*, as in the literary language, are also expressed as an incomplete verb in the form of *-(ā)r edi, bārgān had come*

The present continuous verb is represented by the affix *-jāp*, one *ä* sound is added between the stem of the verb ending in a consonant and this affix, *kelājāppān/ kelājāpmān, orājāpmān, ketājāpmā, oqījāpmān*.

Present-future verbs are used with the affixes *-ä* and *-j*, *bārādi, oqījdi*.

Morphological features of type II Karagkh dialects:

The agreement category has 4 agreements, and the subject-arrival and departure-place-time agreements are represented by the same forms. The accusative agreement is the same as in Type I dialects, and the place-time agreement is also represented by the affix of the destination agreement.

¹ Шоабдурахмонов Ш. Тошкент области ўзбек шевалари. – Т.: Фан, 1976. – Б. 32.

Among the analytical forms used to express the past tense, the form *-(ä)r edi* is expressed in the form of *-mär edi* (not $r > s$) in the case of non-partition, such as *bārmär edi*, *kirmär edi*. This shows that the historical form *-mär*, which expresses indivisibility, is still preserved in the dialect. Also, *-mär* and its back row *-mar* forms have been preserved in Turkmen and Azerbaijani dialects².

The present continuous verb is expressed in *-āp* form, *bārāpmän*, *kelāpmän*. Only *de*, *ye* are used in *-jāp* form for verb bases ending in vowels. In verbs formed with the formative affix *-la*, such as the dialects of the Bukhara group, the *a* in the affix *-la* is dropped and the affix *-āp* is used, *išlāpmän/ iślāmmän*³.

In languages of the Kipchak group, conjugations are mostly used in their entirety. In the dialects of some areas, accusative-accusative agreements are used in one case.

The affixes *-di/-ti*, *-di/-ti* are used to express the definite past tense.

The long past tense is represented by the forms *-gän/-kän/-qan*, as well as by the affix *-gan*, as in the literary language and the Karak dialects of the dialectal zone. In this case, suffixes *-gän/gan* are added to verb bases ending with a voiced consonant, and *-kän/-kan* affixes are added to verb bases ending with a voiceless consonant. *-gän/-kän* is added to front row vowels, and *-kan/-gan* to back row consonants. These affixes are assimilated after the first person singular and plural person-number forms after the base of the verb. For example, *oqıgamman*, like *bargammiz*.

Analytic forms used to express the past tense. *edi* is formed by using the suffix *-ib* (–ō) before the imperfect verb. In this case, the element *b* of the adverb moves to *v* between two vowels, and the incomplete verb *e* is pronounced in the form of long *i*., like *barıvi:dim*, *kelevi:dim*.

Also, after the adjectival affix *-ar*, by using the imperfect verb *edi*, the analytical form in the sense of past continuous is used, *jazarıdim/jazari:dim*, *ojnarıdim/ojnari:dim*. The past tense is formed by adding the affixes *-imiš/-imış* after the adjective forms *gän/-kän/-kan/-gan*, *ke(l)gänimišmän*, *barganımišmıs*. Almost all tenses can be followed by the imperfect verbs *ekän/äkän*, *barganäkän*, *keganäkän*.

The present continuous verb is formed with the affix *-(ä)jāp/-(a)jap*, *barajapti*, *keläjapti*. Also, the affix *-jatir* is used in the speech of the representatives of the older generation, which is not found in the speech of the middle-aged and young generation. This can be assessed as the influence of neighboring Karaganda dialects and literary language.

The present-future tense is formed with the affixes *-(a)j*, *oqıjman*, *surajdi*.

The future tense form is formed by affixing *-a*, *baradi*, *keladi*.

In the Denov sub-dialect zone, there are areas where elements of Kipchak and Qarluq dialects are mixed and used without distinction in these village dialects. These are some streets of Abadon, Hazarbog, newly formed neighborhoods of Koybesh, and in these areas, the form of *āp(qilāpti)* is used together with the present continuous verb *-(ä)jāp/-(a)jap*.

² Амансарыев Ж. Түркмен диалектологиясы. – Ашгабат, 1970. – Б. 349. Нахчыван МССР-ин диалект ва шивэлэри. – Бакы, 1962. – Б. 141.

³ Мирзаев М. Ўзбек тилининг Бухоро группа шевалари. – Т.: Фан. – Б. 58.

References:

1. Ashirboyev S. O‘zbek dialektologiyasi. – Toshkent: Nodirabegim, 2021,176 b
2. Раҳимов С. Ўзбек тили Сурхондарё шевалари (Фонетикаси, Лексикаси). – Тошкент: Фан, 1985.
3. Решетов В.В., Шоабдурахмонов Ш. Ўзбек диалектологияси.- Тошкент: Ўрта ва олий мактаб, 1962.
4. Джураев А. Б. Теоретические основы ареального исследования узбекоязычного массива. – Ташкент: ФАН, 1991.
5. Шоабдурахмонов Ш. Карлукское наречие узбекского языка. – Тошкент: Фан, 1983.
6. Ўзбек халқ шевалари морфологияси. Тошкент: Фан, 1984. – Б. 54.
7. Turdialiyeв A.X. Denov kichik dialektal zonasining xususiyatlariga doir, Oltin bitiglar, 2022. №3.–В. 105-116.
8. Turdialiyeв A.X. Denov qarluqlar shevasida ko‘plik affiksining qo‘llanishi. Ma‘mun akademiyasi. № 2023-6/4.–В. 207-209.

C M R T